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Abstract book

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PEDIATRIC RADIOTHERAPY DEPARTMENT – RECOMMENDATIONS FOR OPTIMAL INFRASTRUCTURE AND PERSONNEL

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Summary

In the multidisciplinary treatment of malignant diseases in the pediatric population, radiotherapy with or without surgery represents the basic modality of local treatment. Although the basic principles of radiotherapy in children are the same as in adults, radiotherapy in children has its specificity because it is applied to an organism in the phase of growth and development. Also, pediatric tumors differ from tumors in adults, so pediatric radiation oncologists have to possess knowledge of pediatric oncology. Treatment of children with malignant diseases requires coordinated work of a multidisciplinary team: radiation oncologists, pediatricians, various specialty surgeons, pathologists, who all participate in the decision-making on combined oncological treatment. Treatment decisions are made in a multidisciplinary environment with the necessary knowledge of all team members.

Pediatric radiation oncology has its specifics and requirements in terms of infrastructure and organization. The basic requirements apply to rooms, equipment, staff, and procedures. Based on international recommendations, the necessary radiotherapy equipment, and its number, for the work with children, are defined. In the treatment of children, it is recommended to use advanced radiotherapy techniques, to avoid the irradiation of healthy tissues as much as possible. Monitoring of early and late adverse effects of radiotherapy is of great importance in treating children with malignant tumors.

Pediatric radiotherapy, as an extremely sophisticated and complex method of treatment, can only be performed in hospitals and centers that can meet all of the above high standards and recommendations

with the coordinated work of a multidisciplinary team with experience in pediatric oncology.

Keywords: pediatric oncology, radiotherapy, department, infrastructure

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